

Algorithmic decision analysis for multi-stage games with incomplete information

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Abstract. Adversarial risk analysis provides decision-theoretic arguments to mitigate common knowledge assumptions in games, thereby improving uncertainty management in competitive decision-making environments. This paper introduces efficient algorithmic approaches to approximate adversarial risk analysis solutions in multi-stage games, covering both sequential and simultaneous settings, through augmented probability simulation. Two security examples concerning international piracy and air combat illustrate the proposed methodology.

Keywords: Adversarial Risk Analysis · Multi-stage games · Augmented probability simulation.

1 Introduction

Adversarial Risk Analysis (ARA) introduces a decision-theoretic framework to solve games by supporting one decision-maker, referred to as the defender (D , she), instead of focusing on all agents simultaneously, as traditionally done in game theory. Specifically, in the context of two agent games, ARA aims to maximize the defender's expected utility, transforming the problem into a decision-analytic one, therefore implementing a Bayesian approach to games in the sense of Kadane and Larkey (1982) and Raiffa (1982), providing procedures to forecast the attacker's (A , he) actions. Its major strength lies in mitigating common knowledge assumptions, including the common prior one in Harsanyi's approach, critically reviewed in Raiffa et al. (2002), Hargreaves-Heap and Varoufakis (2004), or Angeletos and Lian (2018) to name but a few. A comprehensive overview of ARA along with a comparison with standard game-theoretic techniques is provided in Banks et al. (2020). It has been applied in various contexts, including counter-terrorism online surveillance (Gil and Parra-Arnau, 2019), combat modeling enhancement (Roponen and Salo, 2015), and adversarial machine learning Rios Insua et al. (2023).

A significant issue in ARA are the computational challenges it entails, mainly arising from its two-stage process, where the attacker's problem is first simulated

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to generate a probabilistic forecast of his actions and then used to optimize the defender’s strategy. In Ekin et al. (2023), the method of augmented probability simulation (APS, Bielza et al. (1999)) was proposed to solve simple single-stage defend-attack games from an ARA viewpoint, outperforming traditional Monte Carlo methods in scenarios in which the cardinality of the agents’ decision sets is large, even continuous. APS transforms a decision analysis problem into a grand simulation within the combined space of decisions and random variables. It constructs an auxiliary augmented distribution proportional to the product of the utility function and the distributions modeling relevant uncertainties. The optimal decision alternative then coincides with the mode of the marginal of the augmented distribution over the decisions. Consequently, expected utility maximization can be achieved through simulation from the augmented distribution.

This paper studies how to apply APS to solve multi-stage sequential and simultaneous games, supporting the defender in her decision-making, and examines the proposed algorithmic decision analytic (ADA) methodology through security problems related to international piracy and air-combat modelling. Code to reproduce the results provided is available at <https://github.com/jmcamachor1/ADT>.

The ARA framework accommodates various assumptions about the attacker and defender rationality (Banks et al., 2020). In this paper, we limit our analysis to a Defender behaving as a level-2 thinker, as in the Stahl and Wilson (1995) sense: she models A as an strategic player yet assumes that A considers her as non strategic.

2 Multi-stage Sequential Defend-Attack Games

The approach outlined in Ekin et al. (2023) for single stage sequential Defend-Attack games is extended to multiple stages. Of the many possible extensions, we shall adopt the following n -stage sequential game with incomplete information. The defender goes first by selecting a decision $d_1 \in \mathcal{D}_1$; after observing d_1 , the attacker chooses $a_1 \in \mathcal{A}_1$; the defender observes a_1 and makes a decision $d_2 \in \mathcal{D}_2$. This pattern of alternating decisions continues until the n -th stage. After each pair of actions, an uncertainty $\theta_i \in \Theta_i$ influenced by both actions is resolved and becomes known to both players. At the game’s conclusion, each player’s utility is determined by all the actions taken and the uncertainties throughout the game. Figure 1 portrays a bi-agent influence diagram (BAID) for a 2-stage version of the problem, with circles, squares and hexagons, respectively representing uncertainties, decisions and valuations. White nodes refer solely to the Defender, grey ones to the attacker, and striped ones are shared by both agents.

Let $\theta_{:i}$, $a_{:i}$, and $d_{:i}$ respectively designate the sequence of uncertainties, attacks, and defenses up to stage i . In contrast, θ_i , a_i , and d_i denote the sequences from stage i onwards. Furthermore, $h_{:i}$ and h_i represent the complete history of uncertainties and actions taken up to and from stage i , respectively. When any of these sequences are unknown, they are considered sequences of random variables and are represented with uppercase letters; as an example, $\theta_{:i}$ would

Fig. 1: Template for basic 2-stage sequential defend-attack game.

be an instantiation of Θ_i . The Defender's beliefs about θ_i , based on the known sequences $d_{:i}$, $a_{:i}$, and $\theta_{:(i-1)}$, are captured through the probability distribution $p_D(\theta_i|d_i, a_i)$. The utilities of the Defender and Attacker at the final stage are respectively denoted $u_D(d_{:n}, a_{:n}, \theta_{:n})$ and $u_A(d_{:n}, a_{:n}, \theta_{:n})$, reflecting the impact of both agents' actions and the uncertainties throughout the game.

We demonstrate how to solve such n -stage sequential games using APS. Let us start with the simpler case of $n = 2$. Given the history h_1 , which includes the actions and uncertainties from the first stage, the last one can be treated as a typical sequential one-stage defend-attack game, similar to those described in Ekin et al. (2023). These games can be solved using what we shall designate a *single-stage APS*, which requires nesting two APS (one for the Defender, one for the Attacker) as demonstrated in Ekin et al. (2023) and illustrated below. With this algorithm, we can determine the optimal defense strategy for the second stage, denoted as $d_2^*(h_1)$. Additionally, APS provides a mechanism for generating samples from the distribution $p_D(a_2|d_2, h_1)$, which predicts the attacker's actions a_2 in the second stage based on the defensive decisions d_2 and history h_1 .

At the initial stage of the game, the Defender selects a decision $d_1 \in \mathcal{D}_1$ with the goal of maximizing expected utility. This stage is complex because future decisions, including a_1 , d_2 , a_2 , and uncertainties θ_1 and θ_2 , are not yet known and, therefore, modeled as random variables. The Defender's maximum expected utility problem is expressed as

$$d_1^* = \arg \max_{d_1 \in \mathcal{D}_1} \iiint u_D(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) p_D(h_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1) p_D(\theta_1|d_1, a_1) p_D(a_1|d_1) dh_2 d\theta_1 da_1. \quad (1)$$

Assuming we can sample from $p_D(h_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1)$, and that utilities are non-negative, which can be achieved, in general, via a positive affine transformation, let us define the augmented distribution

$$\pi_{D_1}(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) \propto u_D(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) p_D(h_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1) p_D(\theta_1|d_1, a_1) p_D(a_1|d_1).$$

Then, if we are able to generate samples $(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) \sim \pi_{D_1}(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2)$, using the marginal samples of d_1 , a consistent estimator (Chacon, 2020) for the marginal mode of d_1 can be built which, by construction, will coincide with d_1^* .

This sampling can be conducted using a Metropolis-Hastings (MH) algorithm (French and Insua, 2000). Let $(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2)$ be the current state of the chain. We iterate through the following three steps until convergence, where $g_D(\cdot)$ is a proposal generating distribution

1. Propose $\tilde{d}_1 \sim g_D(\cdot|d_1)$.
2. Sample $\tilde{a}_1 \sim p_D(a_1|\tilde{d}_1)$, $\tilde{\theta}_1 \sim p_D(\theta_1|\tilde{d}_1, \tilde{a}_1)$, $\tilde{h}_2 \sim p_D(h_2|\tilde{d}_1, \tilde{a}_1, \tilde{\theta}_1)$.
3. With probability $\min\left(1, \frac{u_D(\tilde{d}_1, \tilde{a}_1, \tilde{\theta}_1, \tilde{h}_2)g_D(d_1|\tilde{d}_1)}{u_D(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2)g_D(\tilde{d}_1|d_1)}\right)$, set the new state of the chain to $(\tilde{d}_1, \tilde{a}_1, \tilde{\theta}_1, \tilde{h}_2)$.

Standard MCMC convergence results (Brooks and Roberts, 1998) show that the stationary distribution of this chain is $\pi_{D_1}(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2)$ under general conditions, supporting the soundness of the approach.

To sample from $p_D(a_1|d_1)$ in step 2 of the algorithm, it is necessary to address the attacker's first-stage problem from the defender's perspective while accounting for all relevant uncertainties. Given d_1 , the attacker seeks to solve

$$\arg \max_{a_1 \in \mathcal{A}_1} \iint u_A(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) p_A(h_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1) p_A(\theta_1|d_1, a_1) dh_2 d\theta_1.$$

Uncertainty about the attacker's probabilities and utilities is modeled using random utilities U_A and probabilities P_A (Banks et al., 2022). This induces uncertainty in the attacker's expected utility and maximizing the corresponding random expected utility yields samples from $p_D(a_1|d_1)$. This problem can be solved defining the random augmented probability distribution (assuming U_A is a.s. non-negative)

$$\Pi_A(a_1, \theta_1, h_2|d_1) \propto U_A(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) P_A(h_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1) P_A(\theta_1|d_1, a_1).$$

It is simple to see that samples from the mode of the random marginal distribution $\Pi_A(a_1|d_1)$ are distributed according to $p_D(a_1|d_1)$. This sampling procedure involves first generating random utilities and probabilities and, then, applying APS, say using another MH algorithm. Additionally, we need to produce samples from $p_D(h_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1)$ based on

$$p_D(h_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1) = p_D(d_2, a_2, \theta_2|h_1) = p_D(\theta_2|d_2, a_2) p_D(a_2|d_2, h_1) p_D(d_2|h_1).$$

Sampling from $p_D(\theta_2|d_2, a_2)$ is standard. Moreover, given h_1 , it is possible to generate samples from $p_D(a_2|d_2, h_1)$ and $p_D(d_2|h_1)$ by implementing a single-stage APS for the sequential game constituted by D_2 and A_2 , conditioned on h_1 . Importantly, at this point, observe that $p_D(d_2|h_1)$ is essentially a point mass at $d_2^*(h_1)$, the optimal decision at stage two based on h_1 . Thus, the proposed single-stage APS provides the required samples from $p_D(h_2|h_1)$, constituted by the APS for D_1 and A_1 , enabling us to solve the sequential game.

In conclusion, solving the first stage of a two-stage sequential game involves a nested structure where two single-stage APS algorithms are utilized. During each iteration of the first-stage APS, it is necessary to run the second-stage APS, conditioning it on the information gathered from the first one. Indeed, the result generalizes to the case with n stages by induction.

Proposition 1. *The n -stage sequential game under incomplete information can be solved using n nested single-stage APS algorithms.*

Proof. We prove the result using induction. The case when $n = 1$ has already been established. Assume now that we can solve an $(n - 1)$ -stage sequential game using APS, which provides us with the means to produce samples from $p_D(h_{2:n}|h_1)$ using $(n - 1)$ nested APS algorithms.

Consider the first stage of the n -stage game. The Defender needs to select $d_1 \in \mathcal{D}_1$ to maximize expected utility. At this stage, the future history $(h_{2:n})$ is unknown and, therefore, treated as a random variable. D must solve the optimization problem

$$\arg \max_{d_1 \in \mathcal{D}_1} \iiint u_D(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_{2:n}) p_D(h_{2:n}|d_1, a_1, \theta_1) p_D(\theta_1|d_1, a_1) p_D(a_1|d_1) dh_{2:n} d\theta_1 da_1,$$

addressed using APS. For this, define the first stage augmented distribution

$$\pi_{D_1}(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_{2:n}) \propto u_D(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_{2:n}) p_D(h_{2:n}|d_1, a_1, \theta_1) p_D(\theta_1|d_1, a_1) p_D(a_1|d_1).$$

Clearly, the mode of the marginal $\pi_{D_1}(d_1)$ coincides with the optimal first-stage decision. By generating samples $(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_{2:n}) \sim \pi_{D_1}(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_{2:n})$, we can construct a consistent estimator of the marginal mode using these d_1 samples. This sampling process involves iterating through a Metropolis-Hastings scheme, similar to the one presented above. Crucially, each iteration of this sampler will require generating samples from $p_D(h_{2:n}|d_1, a_1, \theta_1)$, obtained nesting $(n - 1)$ single-stage APS algorithms, as per our induction hypothesis. Therefore, effectively solving the first stage of an n -stage sequential problem necessitates nesting n single-stage APS algorithms. \triangle

3 Multi-stage Simultaneous Defend-Attack Games

Consider now multi-stage simultaneous defend-attack games with incomplete information. In the setup considered, at the first stage, the Defender chooses $d_1 \in \mathcal{D}_1$, while the Attacker simultaneously selects $a_1 \in \mathcal{A}_1$. Following these actions, the uncertainty $\theta_1 \in \Theta_1$, influenced by both a_1 and d_1 , is resolved and subsequently affects the uncertainty $\theta_2 \in \Theta_2$, which also depends on subsequent actions $d_2 \in \mathcal{D}_2$ and $a_2 \in \mathcal{A}_2$. This pattern of parallel decisions continues until the n -th stage. Finally, the utility of the Defender is contingent upon all her decisions and the uncertainties $\{\theta_i\}_{i=1}^n$, and, similarly, for the Attacker. This setup

can be applied to numerous models, such as the air-combat scenario in Virtanen et al. (2006), or adapted to multi-agent reinforcement learning scenarios, e.g, Gallego et al. (2019). Figure 2 specifies a BAID for a 2-stage simultaneous game.

Fig. 2: Template for basic 2-stage simultaneous defend-attack game BAID.

The methodology for solving these games through APS closely mirrors that used for sequential games. We demonstrate it using the two-stage game. Initially, the Defender aims to maximize expected utility by selecting a decision $d_1 \in \mathcal{D}_1$. At this stage, neither the action a_1 nor the future decisions and uncertainties are known; hence, they are modeled as random variables. The Defender's optimization problem is formally expressed as

$$d_1^* = \arg \max_{d_1 \in \mathcal{D}_1} \iiint u_D(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) p_D(h_2 | d_1, a_1, \theta_1) p_D(\theta_1 | d_1, a_1) p_D(a_1) dh_2 d\theta_1 da_1. \quad (2)$$

Notably, the only difference between this formulation and its sequential counterpart (Eq. 1) is the distribution over the first-stage attack, which is now independent of d_1 due to the simultaneous decision-making feature (i.e., $p_D(a_1)$ vs $p_D(a_1 | d_1)$). Consequently, a similar MH APS algorithm is employed, adjusting only step 2 to sample from $p_D(a_1)$ instead of $p_D(a_1 | d_1)$. To sample from $p_D(a_1)$, consider the Attacker's problem at the first stage, which mirrors the Defender's and is stated as

$$a_1^* = \arg \max_{a_1 \in \mathcal{A}_1} \iiint u_A(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) p_A(h_2 | d_1, a_1, \theta_1) p_A(\theta_1 | d_1, a_1) p_A(d_1) dh_2 d\theta_1 dd_1.$$

As before, uncertainty in the Attacker's utilities and probabilities is accounted for using random utilities U_A and probabilities P_A , generating a random augmented probability distribution that now, as opposed to the sequential case, is

unconditional

$$\Pi_A(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2) \propto U_A(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, h_2)P_A(h_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1)P_A(\theta_1|d_1, a_1)P_A(d_1).$$

Given the minor adjustments required from the sequential to the simultaneous format, it becomes apparent that solving the n -stage simultaneous defend-attack game can be resolved by handled n single-stage APS algorithms.

Proposition 2. *The n -stage simultaneous game under incomplete information can be solved using n nested single-stage APS algorithms.*

The proof of Proposition 2 follows a similar approach and is, therefore, omitted.

4 Computational Issues

The algorithms previously discussed entailed nesting several MH APS schemes, making them computationally intensive. This complexity limits their applicability primarily to games with relatively few stages. To extend these methods to games with a large number of stages, alternative approaches must be considered.

A practical solution for games where decision and uncertainty spaces are discrete and exhibit low cardinality is the implementation of backward induction. Take, for example, the final stage of a two-stage sequential game. Given the history h_1 , it is possible to compute the optimal defense $d_2^*(h_1)$ and sample from $p_D(a_2|d_2, h_1)$ using APS, as explained in Section 2. This process facilitates creating an empirical estimate of $p_D(a_2|d_2, h_1)$. If the cardinality of the decision and uncertainty spaces is sufficiently small, it becomes practical to calculate these quantities for every possible h_1 scenario and store the results. Moving to the first stage in the APS, rather than dynamically invoking the second-stage APS to sample future decisions based on the current h_1 sample, we can simply access and utilize the precomputed values. This method significantly reduces the computational load.

However, the previous approach has its drawbacks, as it can lead to a combinatorial explosion when the cardinality of decision spaces and the number of stages increase. Additionally, while the general approach in Sections 2 and 3 is theoretically applicable to games with continuous decision spaces, the backward induction approach is not. In such cases, it is necessary to develop and employ statistical models that can effectively approximate future optimal decisions and predict attack distributions based on historical data.

Another potential issue that can arise when applying APS occurs when the expected utility surfaces are very flat around the mode. In these situations, the number of required APS samples to resolve the mode could be very high. To address this, we replace the marginal augmented distributions $\pi(h)$ with power transformations $\pi^J(h)$, which are more peaked around the mode. This adjustment facilitates mode identification, see e.g. Müller et al. (2004).

5 Numerical examples

We illustrate the methodologies proposed in the previous sections through two security problems. In particular, the approach for sequential games will be demonstrated through an example on international piracy, whereas the multi-stage simultaneous approach will be conveyed using an air-combat example.

5.1 International piracy

We illustrate practical issues associated with the approach proposed in Section 2 through an example adapted from Sevillano et al. (2012). We support the owner of a ship in managing piracy risks in the Somali coast. The problem is an asymmetric 2-stage sequential game as the one depicted in the BAID in Figure 3. Note that this game is a simplified version of the more general 2-stage sequential problem discussed in Section 2. Here, the second stage attacker decision is omitted, and only one uncertainty is considered. The reason for choosing this simplified version is that it allows us to compare the solutions obtained using the proposed APS scheme with the actual ones provided in Sevillano et al. (2012).

Fig. 3: BAID representing the international piracy example.

In the initial decision-making stage, the ship’s owner proactively selects a defensive strategy (D_1) to mitigate piracy risks, which includes as options deploying varying levels of armed security or opting for a significantly longer alternative route that circumvents the incumbent high-risk area. Subsequently, the Attacker, in response to the Defender’s strategy, decides whether to initiate an attack aimed at hijacking the ship for ransom purposes (A_1). Should the pirates’ operation prove successful (Θ), the ship’s owner is then faced with the decision (D_2) to either pay the ransom, refuse it, or ask the armed forces to recover the ship. The utility of the Defender depends on her strategic choices and the results of pirate attacks on the vessel, while the Attacker’s utility is influenced by his initial decision, the attack’s outcome, and the subsequent decision made by the Defender.

Parametric setup. For full details, see Sevillano et al. (2012). A brief summary is provided here.

Agents. The Defender (D) is the ship owner trying to manage piracy risks. The Attacker (A) are the pirates who decide on eventually seizing the ship to demand a ransom.

Decisions. The alternatives available to D and A are:

- D_1 : Do not implement any protection for the boat (d_1^1), use private protection with one armed person (d_1^2), use private protection with a team of two armed persons (d_1^3), take a more costly alternative route for the trip (d_1^4).
- A_1 : The pirates may choose not to attack the owner's ship (a^0), attack it (a^1), or attack another vessel (a^i). For our problem, consider that there are three additional boats in the region, i.e., $i \in \{2, 3, 4\}$.
- D_2 : Do not respond to the pirates' demands, assuming all associated costs (d_2^1), pay the ransom demanded by the pirates (d_2^2), or request Navy support to release the boat and crew (d_2^3).

Probabilities. The Defender's beliefs about a successful attack ($\Theta = 1$), conditional on $d_1 \in D_1$, are modeled with probabilities $p_D(\Theta = 1|a^1, d_1^1) = 0.4$, $p_D(\Theta = 1|a^1, d_1^2) = 0.1$, and $p_D(\Theta = 1|a^1, d_1^3) = 0.05$. Besides, the Defender assumes that $p_D(\Theta = 1|a^i) = 0.5, i \in \{2, 3, 4\}$.

Defender modeling of Attacker's beliefs. D assesses A 's beliefs about an attack being successful as $P_A(\Theta = 1|a^1, d_1^1) \sim Be(40, 60)$, $P_A(\Theta = 1|a^1, d_1^2) \sim Be(10, 90)$, $P_A(\Theta = 1|a^1, d_1^3) \sim Be(50, 950)$, $P_A(\Theta = 1|a^i) \sim Be(1, 1), i \in \{2, 3, 4\}$; and the Defender's actions after a successful attack as $P_A(D_2|d_1^1, A = a^1, \theta = 1) \sim Dir(1, 1, 1)$, $P_A(D_2|d_1^2, A = a^1, \Theta = 1) \sim Dir(0.1, 4, 6)$, $P_A(D_2|d_1^3, A = a^1, \Theta = 1) \sim Dir(0.1, 1, 10)$, $P_A(D_2|a^i, \Theta = 1) \sim Dir(1, 1, 1)$ for $i = \{2, 3, 4\}$.

Utilities.

- Defender: We employ a constant risk-averse utility function $u_D(d_1, \theta_1, d_2) = -\exp(\rho_D \times c_D(d_1, \theta_1, d_2))$, being ρ_D the risk-aversion coefficient. $c_D(\cdot)$ represents the monetary costs in M € associated with d_1, θ_1 and d_2 (Table 1a). We use $\rho_D = 0.1$ and scale u_D to maintain it positive.
- Attacker: The Defender assumes that the pirates are risk-prone with utility function $u_A(a_1, \theta_1, d_2) = \exp(\rho_A \times c_A(a_1, \theta_1, d_2))$, where $c_A(\cdot)$ represents the costs associated with A_1, Θ_1 , and D_2 in M € (Table 1b) and ρ_A is modeled as $\rho_A \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 20)$. In Table 1b, a^j represents an attack on the Defender when $j = 1$, or on the other boats when $j \in \{2, 3, 4\}$.

Results. Using the proposed methodology, we are able to find the optimal first-stage decision d_1^* and the optimal second-stage decision $d_2^*(d_1^*, a_1, \theta)$ given the first one, the eventual attack and its outcome. The results obtained using APS are analogous to those in Sevillano et al. (2012) using Monte Carlo simulation, demonstrating that both methods yield equivalent solutions. In particular, we find that $d_1^* = d_1^2$, indicating that the optimal proactive measure for the boat owner is to employ private protection with one armed individual. In the second

Table 1: Monetary costs for Defender (c_D) and Attacker (c_A).

(a) $c_D(d_1, \theta_1, d_2)$											(b) $c_A(a_1, \theta_1, d_2)$								
D_1	d_1^1	d_1^1	d_1^1	d_1^1	d_1^2	d_1^2	d_1^2	d_1^2	d_1^3	d_1^3	d_1^3	d_1^3	d_1^4	A_1	a^0	a^j	a^j	a^j	a^j
Θ_1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0			1	1	1	0	
D_2	d_2^1	d_2^2	d_2^3		d_2^1	d_2^2	d_2^3		d_2^1	d_2^2	d_2^3			D_2		1	1	1	
c_D	15.16	2.3	4.28	0	17.25	4.39	6.37	0.05	19.39	6.53	8.51	0.15	0.5	c_A	0	0.97	2.27	-1.28	-0.53

stage, the best course of action, in the event of a successful attack, is to pay the ransom demanded by the pirates ($d_2^* = d_2^2$), as it incurs lower costs for the boat owner compared to either not accepting the pirates' demands (d_2^1) or requesting navy support (d_2^3).

Additionally, we provide the distribution of decisions made by the Attacker in response to the first Defender's decision d_1 illustrated in Table 2. We observe that as the level of proactive measures increases, the probability of the Defender being targeted decreases, indicating that the defense acts as a deterrent. Specifically, when the Defender decides not to implement any protection (d_1^1), the probability of being attacked is very similar to that of the other boats. However, when the Defender employs private protection with a team of two armed personnel (d_1^3), the likelihood of a pirate attack becomes almost negligible. Furthermore, as expected, we observe that when the probability of an attack on the Defender decreases, due to more protective measures or an alternative route, the likelihood of attack is distributed evenly among the other boats. Again, these results are analogous to those in Sevillano et al. (2012).

Table 2: Distribution of optimal decisions for A_1 .

	a_1^0	a_1^1	a_1^2	a_1^3	a_1^4
d_1^1	0.001	0.221	0.283	0.254	0.241
d_1^2	0.009	0.018	0.336	0.297	0.340
d_1^3	0.008	0.001	0.308	0.355	0.328
d_1^4	0.008	0.000	0.327	0.331	0.334

5.2 Air-combat game

Consider a case in which a Defender operates an aerial defense system to protect a strategic infrastructure from an Attacker trying to destroy it. We support D in allocating resources to defend the infrastructure. The problem is structured as in Figure 2. In its initial decision, the Defender will choose (D_1) the number of anti-aircraft missiles to allocate; in turn, the Attacker will decide (A_1) how many drones to deploy, targeting the anti-air defenses of the infrastructure to leave it unprotected against future attacks. Θ_1 represents whether the drones succeed in eliminating the Defender's anti-aircraft missiles. At the second stage, the Defender selects the number of drones to surveil the aerial space of the infrastructure in anticipation of a direct attack. Conversely, the Attacker decides

(A_2) how many drones to send for a bombing targeting the infrastructure. Both decisions, along with the success in neutralizing the anti-air defenses, will determine if the infrastructure is destroyed (Θ_2). The utilities of both the Defender and Attacker will depend on the decisions (D_1, D_2, A_1, A_2) and the uncertainties (Θ_1, Θ_2) with parameters are detailed below.

Parametric setup.

Agents. The Defender (D) allocates resources to protect its infrastructure against aerial attacks. The Attacker (A) aims to select the optimal strategy to destroy such infrastructure.

Decisions. The alternatives available to D and A are:

- D_1 : Install minimal anti-air systems (d_1^1), build a moderate anti-air defense (d_1^2), or a substantial one (d_1^3).
- A_1 : Do not attack the aerial defenses (a_1^1), target the anti-missiles with a few drones (a_1^2), or a high number of drones (a_1^3).
- D_2 : No surveillance (d_2^1), minimal surveillance (d_2^2), or substantial surveillance (d_2^3) by drones.
- A_2 : No direct attack on infrastructure (a_2^1), low-intensity (a_2^2), or high-intensity (a_2^3) attack.

Probabilities. The Defender’s belief about the success of an attack (Θ_1) destroying her anti-air defenses, conditional on d_1 and a_1 , is modeled through the probabilities in Table 3a. Additionally, the probabilities that her infrastructure is destroyed, conditional on a_2, d_2 and whether the attack on the anti-air missiles was successful, are outlined in Tables 3b and 3c.

Table 3: Successful attack probabilities to anti-aerial missiles and infrastructure.

(a) $p_D(\Theta_1=1 d_1, a_1)$	(b) $p_D(\Theta_2=1 d_1, a_1, \Theta_1=1)$	(c) $p_D(\Theta_2=1 d_1, a_1, \Theta_1=0)$																																																
<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="border: none;"></th> <th style="border: none;">a_1^1</th> <th style="border: none;">a_1^2</th> <th style="border: none;">a_1^3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_1^1</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.70</td> <td style="border: none;">0.80</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_1^2</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.35</td> <td style="border: none;">0.45</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_1^3</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.30</td> <td style="border: none;">0.40</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		a_1^1	a_1^2	a_1^3	d_1^1	0.00	0.70	0.80	d_1^2	0.00	0.35	0.45	d_1^3	0.00	0.30	0.40	<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="border: none;"></th> <th style="border: none;">a_2^1</th> <th style="border: none;">a_2^2</th> <th style="border: none;">a_2^3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_2^1</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.85</td> <td style="border: none;">0.95</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_2^2</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.40</td> <td style="border: none;">0.60</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_2^3</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.05</td> <td style="border: none;">0.15</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		a_2^1	a_2^2	a_2^3	d_2^1	0.00	0.85	0.95	d_2^2	0.00	0.40	0.60	d_2^3	0.00	0.05	0.15	<table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="border: none;"></th> <th style="border: none;">a_2^1</th> <th style="border: none;">a_2^2</th> <th style="border: none;">a_2^3</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_2^1</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.25</td> <td style="border: none;">0.35</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_2^2</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.05</td> <td style="border: none;">0.07</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">d_2^3</td> <td style="border: none;">0.00</td> <td style="border: none;">0.01</td> <td style="border: none;">0.02</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		a_2^1	a_2^2	a_2^3	d_2^1	0.00	0.25	0.35	d_2^2	0.00	0.05	0.07	d_2^3	0.00	0.01	0.02
	a_1^1	a_1^2	a_1^3																																															
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Defender modeling of Attacker’s beliefs. D models A ’s beliefs about $\Theta_1 = 1$ as $P_A(\Theta_1|d_1, a_1) \sim \text{Be}(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$, with parameters (σ_1, σ_2) for each d_1 and a_1 displayed in Table 4a. Similarly, D assesses A ’s beliefs about $\Theta_2 = 1$ as $P_A(\Theta_2|d_2, a_2, \theta_1) \sim \text{Be}(\sigma_3, \sigma_4)$, with parameters (σ_3, σ_4) in Tables 4b and 4c. When there is only one number (0 or 1) for the corresponding combination of arguments in a table, it means that a degenerate distribution is used for that number. Additionally, the Defender models the Attacker’s assumptions regarding her decisions to

install anti-air missiles through $P_A(d_1) \sim \text{Dir}(1, 7500, 2499)$. Correspondingly, the Defender assesses the Attacker's beliefs about D_2 using $P_A(d_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1) \sim \text{Dir}(\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3)$, with the corresponding parameters outlined in Tables 5a and 5b.

Table 4: Beta parameters for D 's modeling of A 's beliefs on $\Theta_1 = 1, \Theta_2 = 1$.

(a) $P_A(\Theta_1=1|d_1, a_1)$ (b) $P_A(\Theta_2=1|d_2, a_2, \Theta_1=1)$ (c) $P_A(\Theta_2=1|d_1, a_1, \Theta_1=0)$

	a_1^1	a_1^2	a_1^3
d_1^1	0	(50,50)	(85,15)
d_1^2	0	(20,80)	(30,70)
d_1^3	0	(10,90)	(25,75)

	a_2^1	a_2^2	a_2^3
d_2^1	0	1	1
d_2^2	0	(70,30)	(90,10)
d_2^3	0	(50,50)	(85,15)

	a_2^1	a_2^2	a_2^3
d_2^1	0	(5,95)	(10,90)
d_2^2	0	(2,98)	(8,92)
d_2^3	0	(1,99)	(5,95)

Utilities.

- Defender. We use a constant risk-averse utility function $u_D(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, d_2, a_2, \theta_2) = -\exp(\rho_D \times c_D(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, d_2, a_2, \theta_2))$. c_D denotes the monetary costs related to $d_1, a_1, \theta_1, d_2, a_2$ and θ_2 and ρ_D is the risk-aversion coefficient. We consider that $\rho_D = 0.2$ and scale the utility to ensure it always remains positive.
- Attacker. The Defender posits that the pirates exhibit risk-prone behavior, characterized by the utility function $u_A(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, d_2, a_2, \theta_2) = \exp(\rho_A \times c_A(d_1, a_1, \theta_1, d_2, a_2, \theta_2))$. c_A indicates the costs linked to $d_1, a_1, \theta_1, d_2, a_2$ and θ_2 . To address uncertainties regarding the Attacker’s preferences, ρ_A is modeled as $\rho_A \sim \mathcal{U}(1, 2)$.

Table 5: Dirichlet parameters for D ’s modelling of A ’s beliefs on D_2 .

(a) $P_A(d_2 d_1, a_1, \Theta_1 = 1)$			(b) $P_A(d_2 d_1, a_1, \Theta_1 = 0)$		
	a_1^2	a_1^3		a_1^2	a_1^3
d_1^1	(1,499,9500)	(1,999,9000)	d_1^1	(1000,1000,1000)	(1,4499,4500)
d_1^2	(1,299,9700)	(1,399,9600)	d_1^2	(5000,2500, 2500)	(3500,3500,2000)
d_1^3	(1,99,9900)	(1,199,9800)	d_1^3	(7500,1500,1000)	(2000,3000,8000)

Assume that $c_D(a_1, d_1, a_2, d_2, \theta_1, \theta_2) = f_D(\theta_2) + f_D(\theta_1) + (1 + f_D(a_1))f_D(d_1) + (1 + f_D(a_2))f_D(d_2)$, where f_D is a monetary value function for all decisions and uncertainties for the Defender. Similarly, $c_A(a_1, d_1, a_2, d_2, \theta_1, \theta_2) = f_A(\theta_2) + f_A(\theta_1) - (1 + f_A(d_1))f_A(a_1) - (1 + f_A(d_2))f_A(a_2)$ with f_A being the equivalent of f_D for the Attacker. The expressions for c_D and c_A are in M €. The values of f_D and f_A are displayed in Table 6.

Table 6: Values of f_D and f_A for decisions and uncertainties.

	d_1^1	d_1^2	d_1^3	a_1^1	a_1^2	a_1^3	$\Theta_1=0$	$\Theta_1=1$	d_2^1	d_2^2	d_2^3	a_2^1	a_2^2	a_2^3	$\Theta_2=0$	$\Theta_2=1$
f_D	0.0	0.3	0.6	0.0	0.4	0.5	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.3	1.5	0.0	0.5	0.8	0.0	7.5
f_A	0.0	0.4	0.9	0.0	0.2	0.5	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.45	0.7	0.0	0.85	1.0	0.0	3.5

Results. Optimal defender decisions are found utilizing the proposed approach. We find that the optimal decision for the first stage is to build a moderate anti-air defense ($d_1^* = d_1^2$). Then, for the second stage, we observe that the best decision for the Defender just depends on whether the attack targeting the anti-air defense is successful or not. Specifically, if $\Theta_1 = 1$, the best decision for the Defender would be to protect the infrastructure with maximum defense ($d_2^* = d_2^3$) to prevent its destruction regardless her first decision and the first stage attack. Otherwise, if the attack is not successful, the Defender will always opt to defend with moderate defense ($d_2^* = d_2^2$) in anticipation of a future attack.

We also obtain probabilistic forecasts for the Attacker’s decisions a_1 and a_2 . The distribution of the Attacker’s first-stage action, $p_D(a_1)$, is $(p_A(a_1^1), p_A(a_1^2))$,

$p_A(a_1^3) = (0.000, 0.715, 0.285)$. The probability distribution over the Attacker’s second-stage action, conditioned on the first-stage decisions and uncertainty, $p(a_2|d_1, a_1, \theta_1)$, is presented in Table 7. We observe that the Attacker will always try to destroy the anti-air missiles to facilitate an easier subsequent attack, with the highest probability being that this attack is moderate (a_1^2). Regarding the Attacker’s second stage, we observe different behavior depending on whether the attack on the anti-air missiles is successful or not. In the case of a successful attack, the Attacker is more likely to decide to attack the infrastructure with maximum capacity to complete its destruction. Conversely, if the attack is not successful, the behavior depends on the intensity of the first attack. If this one involved an intense assault (a_1^3), the attacker might decide to either cease the offensive or continue with the attack with similar probability. Alternatively, if the attacker did not target the infrastructure initially, which is unlikely given the forecast A_1^* , they will more likely attack with maximum capacity. If the first attack was moderate (a_1^2), the attacker is also slightly more likely to follow up with a powerful attack.

Table 7: Attacker’s optimal decision distribution for A_2 .

(a) $A_2^*(d_1^*, a_1, \Theta_1 = 1)$		(b) $A_2^*(d_1^*, a_1, \Theta_1 = 0)$			
	a_1^2	a_1^3	a_1^1	a_1^2	a_1^3
d_1^1	(.000,.175,.825)	(.000,.225,.775)	d_1^1	(.078,.100,.822)	(.320,.025,.655) (.485,.047,.468)
d_1^2	(.000,.173,.827)	(.000,.217,.783)	d_1^2	(.004,.145,.815)	(.068,.102,.830) (.513,.045,.442)
d_1^3	(.000,.145,.855)	(.000,.190,.810)	d_1^3	(.012,.188,.800)	(.200,.085,.715) (.500,.045,.455)

6 Discussion

We have provided augmented probability simulation algorithms to solve multi-stage sequential and simultaneous games with incomplete information from an ARA perspective, illustrating them with two examples related to international piracy and air-combat modeling. The algorithms provide not only optimal decisions for the Defender at various stages but also forecasts of the Attacker’s responses. APS algorithms for expected utility maximization could be advantageous in certain situations, as their performance usually scales better with the cardinality of decision sets compared to directly optimizing Monte Carlo approximations of expected utilities, as shown in Ekin et al. (2023).

The methodology proposed could be relevant in security games that model scenarios in Adversarial Machine Learning (Rios Insua et al., 2023), where decision sets are usually continuous and assumptions of complete information are rare. In such settings, ARA provides a natural methodology that effectively handles uncertainty. Similarly, an APS algorithmic approach based on ARA might enhance the modeling of uncertainties related to competitive agents in multi-agent reinforcement learning (Gallego et al., 2019).

In future research, we plan to extend this work to general security games modeled as proper bi-agent influence diagrams, beyond the stylized sequential

and simultaneous templates presented here. We hypothesize that these can be solved by implementing an APS algorithm for each Defender decision in the diagram and a random APS for each Attacker decision. Additionally, we will develop new approaches to handle continuous domains, overcoming the limitations of the current approach. This would lay the foundation for a general algorithmic framework for decision analysis using APS. Such a framework could be integrated into generic software, facilitating practical implementation of ARA support in BAIDs.

Finally, other possible avenues for future research include extending the presented framework to scenarios with multiple attackers and replacing Metropolis-Hastings samplers with Hamiltonian Monte Carlo methods within APS.

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